

MODEL PROJECT-BASED LEARNING UNTUK MENINGKATKAN HASIL BELAJAR DI PERGURUAN TINGGI

Torkis Nasution¹, Ambiyar², Wakhinuddin³

¹Teknik Informatika, STMIK Amik Riau, Jalan Purwodadi Indah KM 10,
Kota Pekanbaru, Riau, Indonesia

^{2,3}Pendidikan Teknologi dan Kejuruan, Universitas Negeri Padang, Jalan Prof. Dr. Hamka,
Air Tawar Barat, Kota Padang, Sumatra Barat, Indonesia

¹e-mail: torkisnasution@sar.ac.id

Submitted
2022-04-24

Accepted
2022-06-23

Published
2022-06-29

Abstrak

Model *Project-Based Learning* (PjBL) diyakini sebagai pendekatan yang menjanjikan untuk meningkatkan pembelajaran mahasiswa di perguruan tinggi. Studi empiris tentang model PjBL telah dibuktikan dengan fokus pada hasil belajar mahasiswa. Hasil afektif berdasarkan persepsi manfaat model PjBL dan persepsi pengalaman model PjBL paling banyak diterapkan yang diukur dengan angket, wawancara, observasi, dan jurnal refleksi diri. Hasil kognitif berupa pengetahuan dan strategi kognitif serta hasil perilaku keterampilan dan keterlibatan dalam kelompok diukur dengan kuesioner, rubrik, tes, wawancara, observasi, jurnal refleksi diri, hasil kerja, dan data log. Hasil keterampilan dan keterlibatan dalam kelompok dinilai dengan rubrik. Tinjauan selanjutnya harus fokus pada investigasi lebih lanjut tentang proses belajar mahasiswa dan produk akhir.

Kata Kunci: PjBL; hasil belajar; perguruan tinggi.

Abstract

The Project-Based Learning (PjBL) model is believed to be a promising approach to improve student learning in higher education. Empirical studies on the PjBL model have been proven with a focus on student learning outcomes. Affective results based on the perceived benefits of the PjBL model and the perceived experience of the PjBL model were most widely applied as measured by questionnaires, interviews, observations, and self-reflection journals. Cognitive outcomes in the form of knowledge and cognitive strategies as well as behavioral outcomes of skills and involvement in groups were measured by questionnaires, rubrics, tests, interviews, observations, self-reflection journals, work results, and log data. Outcomes of skills and involvement in groups are assessed with a rubric. Subsequent reviews should focus on further investigation of the student learning process and the final product.

Keywords: PjBL; study results; higher education.